

Unblocking Odisha's Growth and Development: Addressing the barriers to policy implementation

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Abstract: *Odisha, a state located in the eastern coast of India is ready for growth and development. With its vast natural resources, resilient people and strategic location, it has the potential to become a leading economic hub in the country. To achieve visible growth and sustainable development, it has been introducing many developmental policies and programmes. However, despite its promising outlook, the state encounters significant challenges in implementing its policies into effective outcomes. This article tries to highlight some major obstacles to effective policy implementation in the state and recommends potential solutions for the same to overcome them, which will ultimately pave the way to growth and development of Odisha.*

Keywords: *Development, growth, implementation, policy, programme, barriers, challenges, red tape, corruption*

Introduction

Odisha, previously known as Orissa, is one of India's 29 states, located in the Eastern part of India. It is bordered on the west and north by Chattishgarh, on the east by West Bengal, on the north by Jharkhand, and on the south by Andhra Pradesh. From Balesore to Ganjam, Odisha has 485 kilometers of shoreline along the Bay of Bengal on its east coast. As per the 2011 Census, it is the 11th most populated state in the country and the 9th largest in terms of area. In the case of the tribal population, Odisha is India's third most tribal populous state. It has also enriched with vast natural resources that attracting huge investors from overseas to invest in Odisha. With its vast natural resources, resilient people and strategic location, it has the potential to become a leading economic hub in the country. To achieve visible growth and sustainable development, it has been introducing many developmental policies and programmes in the state.¹

The Government of India since independence has been introducing many schemes for the overall development of the nation covering all fields of development like the economy, health, agriculture, social,

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political, industrial, banking, rural and urban sector, women, and child development, etc. With the collaboration of states governments, all schemes of development have been implemented in all parts of the country. There are tons of national as well as state development policies and programmes that have been introduced in Odisha to develop the overall conditions of the state. Some of the major schemes of the government of India like National Rural Health Mission (NRHM), National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM), Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGA) which is renamed as VB-G RAM G that stands for Vikshit Bharat- Guarantee for Rozgar and Ajeevika Mission (Gramin) in 2025, Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana and many more are now active in Odisha. Likewise, some of the major developmental schemes those are now running in Odisha are Krushak Assistance for Livelihood and Income Augmentation Scheme (KALIA), Bhoochetana, Amulya Yojana, Subhadra Yojana, Odisha Food Security Scheme (OFSS), Biju Swasthya Kalyan Yojana (BSKY), Utthan Scheme etc.

Development is a pre-requisite condition for the growth of a country. It requires strategic planning and its implementation along with proper evaluation. Then only we can see visible and expected result. Policy implementation is one of the important stages of policy process. There are various implementing agencies in India like central implementing agencies, state implementing agencies and local implementing agencies. At the central level, government ministries and departments are responsible for implementing development policies and programmes. Likewise, at the state level, there are state government ministries and departments holding the responsibility of policy implementation. And finally at the local level, both urban local-self-governments (The Municipalities) and rural local-self-governments (The Panchayats) bear the responsibility to implement development policies and projects in their respective areas.

1. Barriers In the Implementation of Developmental Policies and Programmes:

Currently, several developmental policies and programmes are being implemented in Odisha to promote growth and development across all key sectors. However, it is facing many challenges in their way of successful implementation, which must be addressed as soon as possible for speedy growth and development of the state. Some of the major obstacles of policy implementation are discussed below:

1.1.Lack of awareness and information: Availability of sufficient information regarding any development schemes and its benefits can lead to its better implementation at any level of government. Many policies and programmes have launched by the government mainly for the poor people of India. However, due to lack of information on different policies, the needy sections of the society are not able to get full benefits from those development policies. It is the duty of the local

government to circulate all necessary information and guidelines to the targeted sections of the society. At the village level, it is the responsibility of the Gram Panchayats as they are the implementing agencies at the grass-root level to provide such information to all village dwellers. Through meetings, gram panchayats are conducting awareness programs regarding various government policies and programmes and also providing information about the benefits of all schemes that are introduced in any village panchayats. However, these awareness programs and information provided are insufficient as a result of which many village people don't have enough information about various policies and are not fully aware of them that results the delay in getting benefits from any development policy.

1.2. Corruption: Corruption is one of the major problems that is posing the threat to the development of our nation. It has become so rampant that no area is left out from its convergence. The success of any policy absolutely depends upon the proper execution of a policy. But due to corruption, proper implementation of any policy cannot be achieved. The actual funds that reach to the beneficiaries are comparatively very little to the funds released for the development of a scheme. Corruption at local levels is the reason for the lack of proper implementation of any developmental policy.

1.3. Lack of political will and intervention: Lack of political will and intervention is a challenge which is posing threat to the proper implementation of development policies at the grass-root level. The intervention of many politicians in the working of local government agencies in the local areas often leads to the dysfunction of governmental activities. It is found that politicians are often involved in the corrupt practices with local authorities to achieve their self-interest. They put their self-interest over and above the interest of the people. Due to lack of political will, many policies face delay in their implementation.

1.4. Lack of administrative will: The bureaucracy is responsible for the efficient administration of development through both the formulation and implementation of development plans, projects, programmes and policies; therefore, strong administrative will is essential for the successful implementation of policies as administrators are entrusted with executing development and welfare measures for the socio-economic development of the nation. However, due to lack of administrative will to fully implement any policies on the part of executing authorities, the fruits of any welfare policy cannot able to reach to the needy sections for whom those development policies are being formulated.

1.5. Financial resources: The financial resources for implementation of various central government policies are devolved to districts through the corresponding states. Many times funds stuck at the

state level due to various administrative and political reasons for which district administration face financial constraints to implement various policies in time. Even in case of direct transfer of funds to district administration by central or state government get delayed that leads to delay in the implementation of various policies.

1.6. Lack of Infrastructure: Lack of adequate infrastructural development is also posing a challenge to the implementation of policies at the grass-root level. This involves roads, drinking water supply, primary health care centres, schools, electricity etc. Lack of connectivity of remote villages from district excludes them from getting benefitted by many development and welfare schemes. For example, due to poor conditions of primary health care centres, health scheme like National Rural Health Mission is not able to improve health conditions in rural areas.

1.7. Lack of Human resource and skills: Lack of Human resources is the most important problem that needs to give special attention while implementing a policy. Manpower, both in quantity and quality, is very much necessary for achieving targets set out in a policy. But due to lack of sufficient human resource and skills, many development schemes are facing problem of implementation. It also adversely effects on the plan preparation, scrutiny, monitoring and evaluation at the block and gram panchayats level.

1.8. Lack of planning and coordination: Though government schemes provide broader guidelines to be followed by all levels of government, yet at the district level, planning is essential for implementing a scheme by taking into consideration of various developmental parameters. Many times, remote and backward areas like certain blocks and villages of district get ignored during this process. Thus, planning is not inclusive and needy people do not get benefits from various welfare schemes.

1.9. Field level monitoring and beneficiary verification: Insufficient monitoring of policy implementation on the part of Central as well as State government is one of the major problems in the poor implementation of development policies both at the district and village level. For example, due to lack of proper monitoring and verification of beneficiaries, many policies implementation suffered from this mistake. Taking the examples of Public Distribution System and MGNREGA, studies found the lack of verification of beneficiaries while providing benefits under the schemes; as a result, the needy ones are excluded from the list.

1.10. Discrimination on the basis of caste and gender: Though the Constitution of India guarantees no discrimination on the basis of caste, creed, religion, place of birth and gender under article 15, in reality, discrimination mainly on the basis of caste and gender is acting as a big threat

that hinders the way of reaching benefits to all needy persons, mainly women and vulnerable sections of the society. Dominating caste groups, plotting with district administration and political parties, snatch the benefits of development schemes for which the needy groups are excluded.

- 1.11. Effective evaluation and feedback mechanism:** Policy evaluation and feedback mechanism aim to study the effectiveness of policy implementation. Implementing agencies often focus more on procedural aspects than on the effectiveness of policies, which makes policy implementation complex and cumbersome. Even, most of the development schemes do not have effective evaluation and feedback mechanism to examine the effectiveness of policies and to know the feedback from targeted groups and beneficiaries. Thus, the scope of improvement becomes stagnant.
- 1.12. Grievance redressal mechanism:** No administration can claim itself as an accountable and responsible administration, unless and until it has effective and efficient grievance redressal mechanism to solve complaints and grievances lodged by the people. Due to many reasons like absence of incentives, low morale of the services, negligence in administration, lack of proper authority and delay in providing services are some of the reasons that put aggrieved people to complaint about their grievances. Many a time, the actual reason of grievance is in internal disorganization of the system and failure to solve simple systematic solutions.
- 1.13. Delay:** Due to many reasons like insufficient funds, lack of skilled manpower, lack of political and bureaucratic will, lack of coordination and cooperation in implementing agencies, many welfare and development projects and schemes get delayed in their implementation which in turns delay the development process of the poor and vulnerable sections of the society. For successful implementation of a policy, it requires to achieve its targets within stipulated time, so that administration can use that extra time in other developmental activities.
- 1.14. Faulty fund management:** There is faulty fund management in the implementation of various development policies by state governments which leads to improper and ineffective implementation of many schemes and as such, the needy poor people are suffering from it because of not getting benefits within time from different welfare schemes.
- 1.15. Deficiencies in planning:** Planning is the base of any successful policy formulation and implementation. It determines the means through which the ends can be achieved. Deficiencies in planning at all levels of government often lead to the poor implementation of policies and programmes. Many welfare and development policies face structural as well as functional problems

only because of lack of planning at different levels of government which leads to the slow development of socio-economic conditions of the poor and targeted sections of the society.

2. Suggestions

The following are some suggestions to improve better implementation of development policies and programmes:

- 2.1. **Awareness programmes:** Awareness programmes for beneficiaries should be conducted at regular basis at the grass-root level by the government regarding aims and benefits of different government schemes and policies. Beneficiaries should be provided with all important information regarding all policies they are availing by executive authorities.
- 2.2. **Anti-corruption measures:** Adequate measures should be taken by the government at all levels to remove corruption in formulating and implementing different policies, programmes and projects.
- 2.3. **Timely provision of financial resources:** Financial resources should be provided within time to district administration so that, there will not be any financial problems while implementing the government policies at grass-root level.
- 2.4. **Strong political will:** Political leaders should refrain themselves from indulging corrupt practices so that the actual aim of all government policies and programmes can be achieved and benefits also can be reached to the needy beneficiaries. There should be a strong political will on the part of all political leaders to actually do service for the people in general and Nation in particular.
- 2.5. **Strong administrative will:** The executive authorities should also have strong will to implement government policies and programmes so that people can be easily benefitted by those developmental and welfare policies.
- 2.6. **Improving administrative capabilities through training:** There is a need to improve administrative capabilities by government mainly at the grass-root levels that can lead to the speedy implementation of policies, programmes and projects. Therefore, training should be an integral part of government employees who are dealing with the implementation of all governmental policies and programmes. Therefore, government should conduct training programmes for the line staffs from time to time.
- 2.7. **Recruitment of technically skilled people:** Though there is deficiency of skilled and technical manpower mainly at the block and Panchayat level, necessary measures and actions should be taken by the government to recruit technically skilled people into the service.

- 2.8. **Infrastructure development:** Improving infrastructure development like roads, electricity, primary health care, drinking water supply etc. must be given priorities by the government because without it, the aims and objectives of government policies cannot be achieved.
- 2.9. **Planning:** It should be inclusive in nature, so that benefits of the government schemes can be reached to the required area covering all needy sections of a society.
- 2.10. **Coordination and cooperation:** To achieve any developmental goal, both coordination and cooperation play a very crucial role. Therefore, coordination and cooperation within various departments at the district level is required to avoid any overlapping and confusions that may create problems in implementing the government policies and programmes.
- 2.11. **Strong and strict laws:** Strong and strict laws must be introduced and executed by the government as soon as possible that can punish those who are practicing any kind of discrimination mainly on the basis of caste and gender while providing basic services to the people.
- 2.12. **Strengthening field level monitoring mechanism:** Sufficient field level monitoring should be done by both the central and state government to avoid any sorts of problems arising during the implementation of government policies.
- 2.13. **Policy evaluation:** It is an integral part in the successful implementation of a policy. Therefore, government both at the central and state levels must have effective policy evaluation mechanism or feedback mechanism to monitor the progress of government schemes that would lead to the better implementation of policies.
- 2.14. **Strengthen Grievance Redress Mechanism:** Government should strengthen its Grievance Redress Mechanism so that it can speed up its actions in redressing grievances of the beneficiaries that will lead to the effectiveness of the administration and good governance.
- 2.15. **Speeding up policy formulation and implementation:** Many times, the targets set o by the government for different policies are not achieved due to delays in the process of policy formulation and implementation. So, the government should speed up its process to achieve the target within stipulated time.
- 2.16. **Active participation of people:** The most important role in the successful implementation of any development policies and programmes is the active participation of people. Without this no development can be achieved.

Conclusion

Odisha while has achieved visible success in many areas of development like agriculture, health, education, infrastructure etc, it has been facing some deep-rooted barriers that are hindering in the way of fuller implementation of developmental policies and programmes. Therefore, these obstacles must be addressed within time with better governance, strategic planning, resource allocation and active participation of people that will help the state to achieve its true potential that will lead to its ultimate growth and development.

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